

HARNESSING WASTE HEAT AND SOLAR THERMAL INTEGRATION FOR SUSTAINABLE BREWERY COOLING: A CASE STUDY APPROACH

Musannif Shah¹, Valeria Palomba¹, Andrea Frazzica¹, Mikel Arenas-Larrañaga², Daniel Carbonell^{2,3}

¹Istituto di Tecnologie Avanzate per l'Energia CNR ITAE, 98126, Messina, Italy,
musannif.shah@itae.cnr.it, valeria.palomba@cnr.it, andrea.frazzica@cnr.it

²SPF Institut für Solartechnik, OST – Ostschweizer Fachhochschule, CH-8640 Rapperswil,
Switzerland, mikel.arenas@ost.ch, extern.carbonell@ost.ch

³DCarbo Energy Consulting S.L., 08212, Sant Llorenç Savall, Barcelona, Spain,
daniel.carbonell@dcarbo.es

ABSTRACT

Industrial waste heat refers to the thermal energy generated in an industrial process that is not put into practical use and is either lost, wasted, or dumped. The brewery industry consumes a significant amount of energy, mostly dedicated to cooling purposes. This paper explores a novel hybrid design that harnesses thermal energy from potential wastewater sources and integrates high vacuum flat plate (HVFP) solar thermal collectors with adsorption cooling technology to provide process cooling in a specific brewery case study (Browar Glubczyce). The studied brewery produces up to 50000 m³ of beer annually. Following each wort boiling cycle, the entire volume is cooled to fermentation temperature (e.g., 8 °C). The proposed system exploits thermal power (e.g., 350 kW) from wastewater sources at approximately 80 °C, supplemented by an array of 70 kW HVFP thermal collectors to augment the primary heat source, raising the supply temperature to 100 °C for a 200-kW capacity adsorption chiller. A preliminary analysis based on the simulation of this hybrid system suggests potential annual energy savings and reductions in CO₂ emissions.

Key Words: *Waste heat recovery, Low-grade heat, Brewery, Adsorption cooling.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The potential of low-grade waste heat and solar thermal technologies for industrial cooling remains less explored. In 2020, the industrial sector in the European Union (EU) accounted for 26.1% of the total energy consumption. The primary energy sources employed for fulfilling this demand are electricity (32.9%) and fossil fuels (48.5%), leading to a substantial dependence on fossil fuels, predominantly imported from non-EU countries [1]. Approximately, 150 TWh/y of electricity is used for process cooling [2], primarily in industries such as food and beverage, tobacco, and light chemicals. In these industries, cooling can account for up to 50% of electricity consumption, typically for temperatures above 0 °C. The industrial cooling energy market is projected to experience a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 6.1% in the US market between 2023 and 2033 [3].

Breweries are large-scale industrial facilities that consume a significant amount of energy. Brewing and fermentation are both considered energy-intensive processes in beer production. In particular, brewing requires a significant amount of heat demand, with the wort kettle alone accounting for one-third of the steam used by the entire plant. Additionally, the fermentation process demands a

considerable amount of cooling energy, constituting approximately 60 to 70% of the total cooling capacity, which is supplied by a refrigeration system [4].

Conventionally, vapor compression chillers powered by electricity continue to dominate the industrial process cooling market due to their widespread availability and reliability, while thermally-driven technologies are limited to a niche market [5]. However, approximately 300 TWh/y of waste heat sources are available from industrial processes in the EU [6]. From this waste heat, around 35% is below 200 °C leaving a significant potential for integrating thermally driven cooling technologies. In addition, the adoption of solar thermal energy to support the supply of cooling energy is increasingly appealing due to its sustainability, technical feasibility, and economic advantages. However, its implementation is still limited [7].

The industrial sector presents favourable conditions for the use of solar thermal energy, as the load is often consistent throughout the year and existing storage facilities can be utilized. However, despite these advantages, the adoption of solar thermal systems in industrial companies remains limited globally, with such systems accounting for only 12% of the installed capacity worldwide [8]. Therefore, it is essential to explore the potential of integrating solar thermal energy based on the For such applications, adsorption cooling systems are considered highly reliable thermally driven cooling technologies due to their numerous advantages [9]. These systems can operate using low-grade waste heat, utilize natural refrigerants like water, have minimal moving mechanical parts, require low maintenance, and are environmentally friendly [10].

This paper focuses on a case study to assess the potential of low-grade thermal energy recovery in cooling applications for the brewery industry. This work proposes a novel hybrid system that uses thermal energy from the hot wort stream and solar thermal collectors to operate an adsorption chiller. Moreover, the study also aims to evaluate the energy performance of the system and optimization of the key components of the system using pytrnsys simulation tool [11].

2. MAIN BODY

The proposed system demonstrates a solution for thermally driven industrial cooling technology based on the adsorption process, being able to exploit low-grade waste and renewable energy, to increase the overall energy performance and efficiency of the system. The main objective of this work is to propose a cost-competitive industrial cooling solution for a case study brewery industry

FIGURE 1: Operational control of the system

(e.g., Browar Glubczyce, Poland). The analysis of the system is being carried out in pytrnsys, a Python-based framework based on TRNSYS called pytrnsys [11]. This tool allows to develop, run, and post-process of TRNSYS simulations in a more user-friendly way. The brewery case study has an annual beer production capacity of up to 50,000 m³. The mashing and boiling are conducted by heating 35 m³ of beer wort using process steam approximately 800 times per year. Afterward, the entire volume of the wort is cooled from 98 °C to the fermentation temperature of 8 °C within an average duration of 2 hours for each batch, achieved through a two-stage cooling process. The operational control of the batch-wise cooling of the wort is shown in the Figure 1. In the first stage, the cooling water sourced from a deep well at 15 °C lowers the wort temperature, whereas, in the later stage, an adsorption chiller cools further the wort to the required temperature. The system also comprises an existing ammonia cooling system needed to reach the final temperature. The estimated cooling capacity of the adsorption chiller for the temperature range of 6/15 °C and flow rate of 17.1 m³/h is 200 kW. Figure 2 shows the schematic layout of the proposed system. A series of heat exchangers (HE) are installed to lower the temperature of the wort after the mashing stage from 98 °C to 8 °C. For instance, a closed loop of water recovers thermal energy from hot wort (e.g., HE1) to supply the driving thermal energy to the adsorption chiller followed by a supplementary array of solar thermal collectors to achieve the design driving temperature of the chiller. The cooling water that comes from the deep well at 15 °C is chilled in an adsorption chiller and supplied at 6 °C (point 10) to HE2 which cools down the wort to the required temperature. The ammonia chiller is only activated when the adsorption chiller is not able to achieve the wort set point temperature.

3. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

The proposed system layout for the case study brewery at Browar Glubczyce, Poland showcases the integration of waste heat recovery from process wort and solar thermal technologies to meet the brewery's cooling demands. The implementation of an adsorption chiller driven by the recovered thermal energy from the hybrid system is expected to yield significant energy savings and reduce

FIGURE 2: Schematic layout of the system

CO₂ emissions. Preliminary simulations indicate potential annual electricity savings from 64 MWh to 161 MWh and a reduction of 51 t/y of CO₂ emissions at full plant operation.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement No 101138697 (RE-WITCH)

REFERENCES

- [1] “Final energy consumption in industry - detailed statistics - Statistics Explained.” Accessed: Mar. 25, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Final_energy_consumption_in_industry_-_detailed_statistics#Paper.2C_pulp_and_printing_industry
- [2] M. Rehfeldt, C. Rohde, T. Fleiter, F. Toro, and F. Reitze, “A bottom-up estimation of heating and cooling demand in the European industry”.
- [3] “Industrial Cooling Systems Market Size, Share & Trends | 2033.” Accessed: Mar. 25, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.futuremarketinsights.com/reports/industrial-cooling-systems-market>
- [4] “Efficient use of energy and resource through conservation and recovery in breweries”.
- [5] M. Kılıç, “Evaluation of Combined Thermal–Mechanical Compression Systems: A Review for Energy Efficient Sustainable Cooling,” *Sustain.*, vol. 14, no. 21, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.3390/SU142113724.
- [6] M. Papapetrou, G. Kosmadakis, A. Cipollina, U. La Commare, and G. Micale, “Industrial waste heat: Estimation of the technically available resource in the EU per industrial sector, temperature level and country,” *Appl. Therm. Eng.*, vol. 138, no. July 2017, pp. 207–216, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2018.04.043.
- [7] L. Kumar, M. Hasanuzzaman, and N. A. Rahim, “Global advancement of solar thermal energy technologies for industrial process heat and its future prospects: A review,” *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 195, pp. 885–908, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.1016/J.ENCONMAN.2019.05.081.
- [8] D. Tschopp, Z. Tian, M. Berberich, J. Fan, B. Perers, and S. Furbo, “Large-scale solar thermal systems in leading countries: A review and comparative study of Denmark, China, Germany and Austria,” *Appl. Energy*, vol. 270, p. 114997, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.APENERGY.2020.114997.
- [9] A. Capri, A. Frazzica, and L. Calabrese, “Recent Developments in Coating Technologies for Adsorption Heat Pumps: A Review,” *Coatings 2020, Vol. 10, Page 855*, vol. 10, no. 9, p. 855, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.3390/COATINGS10090855.
- [10] V. Palomba, A. Bonanno, V. Brancato, A. Frazzica, and R. Herrmann, “Design of adsorption chillers under rolling conditions in naval applications: Experimental and numerical approaches,” *Appl. Therm. Eng.*, vol. 248, p. 123224, Jul. 2024, doi: 10.1016/J.APPLTHERMALENG.2024.123224.
- [11] “pytrnsys — pytrnsys documentation.” Accessed: Mar. 27, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://pytrnsys.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>